

Personal data

*Vereist

1. Which of the data in the address book are personal data? (multiple answers possible) *

Vink alle toepasselijke opties aan.

- Name
- Address
- Phone number
- Email address
- IP address
- Blood type
- Eye colour
- Age
- Height

Well done! Any data collected from or about people are personal data.

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Studies with personal data

Last year five studies were conducted in which personal data were collected:

- A. This study collected participants' age
- B. This study collected participants' place of birth
- C. This study collected participants' IP address
- D. This study collected participants' eye colour
- E. This study collected participants' blood type

Put the studies in chronological order. You are given the following clues:

The second study did not collect IP addresses or blood types
The largest study was the study collecting eye colour
The study collecting blood types was conducted before the study collecting IP addresses
The study collecting places of birth was not the last study

The study collecting ages was conducted after the study
collecting IP addresses
The largest study was conducted first

2. What is the correct order of the studies? Write your answer as A-B-C-D-E *

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